

Past to Future

Towards fully paleo-informed future climate projections

P2F website

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Cardiff University

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Abstract	The first version of the P2F website has been launched on the internet

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1. Summary

This document provides an overview of the development and launch of the public website for the P2F project: <https://past2future.org/>.

The website hosting is discussed, and the *basic* structure and design of the website are provided. Since this is a first version of the website, future development plans are also laid out in this document and management responsibilities are written down. More information on the design and layout of the current pages are given in the Appendix.

2. Past to Future website hosting

The domain name www.past2future.org was offered to us by Prof. dr. Chris Brierley from University College London. The domain name was created as part of the Paleoclimate Modelling Intercomparison Project (PMIP) working group but was not in use anymore. Together with the Information and Technology Services (ITS) of Utrecht University the transfer of the domain name was arranged, and the website is now being hosted by Utrecht University.

For creating and managing the website the content management system (CMS) WordPress is used. Within Utrecht University's WordPress environment, a self-designed theme called 'UU Drift' is available. Making use of the theme, enabled us to quickly set up our website and customize it to the P2F branding. For creating and editing content we make use of default editor Gutenberg.

3. Design and structure

3.1 Overview

The website serves as the central hub for all project-related information and features a branded, visually engaging interface that will link directly to the project's data portal and will showcase a wide range of resources once available. These include research outputs, paper lay summaries, blogs, press releases, outreach materials, presentation slides, and recordings.

The basic design of the website has been structured around the following topics (pages are represented in bold):

- About
 - **About P2F**
 - **Team & Partners**
 - **Scientific Themes**
- Activities
 - **News**
 - **Events**
- Results
 - **Data Portal**
 - **Publications**
- **P2F Internal**
- **Contact**

These topics and the associated pages are visible and accessible via a menu on top of every page, including a quick link to the home page reached by pressing on the P2F logo in the top right corner. Layout design is optimised for both mobile and desktop usage.

On the home page an overview of the most important project-related information is provided with quick links to the other pages on the website that contain more detailed information.

“ We are heading towards a climate state on Earth that has not been observed by (human-made) measurements before, and thus information on past climatic states becomes increasingly more important to help anticipate future Earth System change.”

— Anna von der Heydt, Project Coordinator

About Past to Future

How can climate history help us create a more accurate picture of the future climate? Starting from March 2025, P2F researchers will spend the next four years working intensively to answer this question.

READ MORE ABOUT P2F

Consortium

The consortium includes 21 European partners and 3 associated partners from Switzerland, the US and Australia, covering a broad range of fields from mathematics, physics, geology, (paleo-)biology and archaeology.

OUR TEAM & PARTNERS

Figure 1 Home page (part 1)

Horizon Europe

The project received € 14.9 million from the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme for research and Innovation.

FIND ALL PROJECT RESULTS ON THE EU WEBSITE

Latest News

20/03/2025

An exciting launch for the P2F Team

More News

Upcoming Events

05/11/2025

General Assembly #1

More Events

P2F focuses on four Scientific Themes

Figure 2 Home page (part 2)

Figure 3 Home page (part 3)

The acknowledgment of the EU funding is included in the Footer of the website, to ensure this is clearly visible on every page.

A screenshot and description of each page is provided in Appendix 1. Over the course of the project more (sub)pages might be added.

For the visual design of the website, we used the P2F colour scheme while taking in consideration WordPress' suggestions on colour combination for best readability.

Figure 4 P2F colour scheme

3.2 Further development plans

The existing website layout provides the groundwork for additional content to be shared over the course of the project. Once additional resources and content become available for the website, they will help inform further development and adjustments to the design and layout of certain pages (such as the news and events sections) as well as the overall website structure.

A key design element we still intend to develop involves offering tailored entry points for different audiences to ensure accessibility and relevance across sectors, thereby enhancing stakeholder engagement.

Update plans for specific pages are mentioned in Appendix 1.

4. Website Management

The project management team at Utrecht University (UU) and the Public Engagement and Impact Manager at Cardiff University (U.Cardiff) will jointly be responsible for website updates and maintenance. UU is responsible for updating the P2F internal page and all project related news, events and other updates. U.Cardiff is responsible for generating and updating content related to dissemination, exploitation and communication.

For technical aspects and issues, we will rely on the support of ITS at Utrecht University. To this point they have shown to be very responsive and open to suggestions on the theme. They have reacted promptly to fix the functional issues we have reported so far and have accommodated our wishes for adjustments to the 'UU Drift' theme.

5. Appendix 1: pages

5.1 About P2F

The *About P2F* page contains key information on the aim of the project, such as the motivation behind the project, the main goal and objectives, and the relevance of the project.

Past 2 Future
Towards fully paleo-informed future climate projections

About ▾ Activities ▾ Results ▾ P2F Internal Contact

About P2F

Past to Future (P2F) is a 4-year Horizon Europe research project which launched in March 2025 and brings together 24 partners from a wide-range of disciplines in future climate model development, paleo-climate data collection, and applied mathematics. Our goal is to make optimal use of past climatic information to better understand Earth's climate response to various kinds of forcing, focusing on abrupt climate transitions and tipping points.

Advancing our knowledge of past climatic conditions to better understand the future

P2F addresses the critical challenge of enhancing our capacity to anticipate future climate change by radically advancing our knowledge of past climatic conditions. As the Earth moves towards climate states not covered by human-made observations, understanding past climate responses to various forcings, particularly abrupt transitions and tipping points, becomes increasingly vital. Current Earth System Models (ESMs) are primarily calibrated using relatively stable instrumental records of the last ~170 years, limiting their ability to accurately simulate potentially exotic future climate states characterised by significant variability and critical transitions.

Figure 5 About P2F page (part 1)

The overarching ambition of P2F is to develop, expand, and utilise the wealth of paleoclimate data to significantly improve existing ESMs. This involves pioneering methods to directly integrate paleoclimate data into the model development phase, a crucial step towards creating fully paleo-informed models for future projection. By reconstructing past climate evolution and identifying the leading dynamical processes and feedbacks, P2F aims to enhance the ability of ESMs to model and anticipate critical transitions in the climate and ecosystems at relevant spatio-temporal scales.

These simulations, carried out with a hierarchy of models focusing on different time scales, will arguably be the most robust climate simulations ever carried out.

— Past 2 Future

Objectives

Through our objectives listed below, P2F strives to fundamentally advance our ability to understand and anticipate the main climatic and societal impacts of the ongoing climate crisis, ultimately informing mitigation and adaptation strategies and contributing to a more resilient future. The project will actively engage with stakeholders and ensure open access to its findings, data, and models, fostering a lasting impact on climate science and policy.

1. Determine key processes and drivers of past climate changes including spatio-temporal variability and abrupt transitions as well as their impact on ecosystems and early societies.
2. Extend the reach of Earth System Models by providing fully paleo-informed models for future projections.
3. Produce a portfolio of plausible future climate change scenarios taking advantage of documented past climate changes and abrupt transitions.
4. Identify and understand tipping points and high-impact/low-likelihood events.
5. Efficiently disseminate research outputs and engage key stakeholders in dialogue to ensure appropriate synergies are attained.

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Go to: About P2F, Team & Partners, Scientific Themes, News, Events, Data Portal, Publications, P2F Internal

Contact: Project Manager: Dr. Stefanie Weira, Utrecht University, p2f@uu.nl

Follow us

Figure 6 About P2F (part 2)

5.2 Team & Partners

On the *Team & Partners* page, logos of all beneficiaries and associated partners are provided as well as links to project collaborators. Additional collaborators will be added throughout the duration of the project.

Team & Partners

The consortium includes 21 European partners and 3 associated partners from Switzerland, the US and Australia, covering a broad range of fields from mathematics, physics, geology, (paleo-)biology and archaeology.

Figure 7 Team & Partners page (part 1)

P2F Beneficiaries

Utrecht University, the Netherlands	University of Copenhagen, Denmark	Technical University of Munich, Germany	University of Leicester, United Kingdom
Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland, Denmark	University of Leeds, United Kingdom	Complutense University of Madrid, Spain	University of Bristol, United Kingdom
Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany	University of Durham, United Kingdom	University of Exeter, United Kingdom	Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany
Cardiff University, United Kingdom	Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, Germany	MetOffice, United Kingdom

Figure 8 Team & Partners page (part 2) - please note that not all beneficiaries are captured on this screenshot.

P2F Associated Partners

University of Bern, Switzerland	University of Adelaide, Australia	National Science Foundation National Center for Atmospheric Research, United States

Project Collaborations

P2F in particular collaborates closely with the following initiatives and EU-funded projects:

ClimTip – Understanding and assessing climate tipping points	TipESM – Exploring tipping points and their impacts using Earth System models

Figure 9 Team & Partners page (part 3)

5.3 Scientific Themes

The four scientific work streams of the project are highlighted on the *Scientific Themes page* and a short description is given to explain the main tasks of each workstream. In addition, a link to the general P2F poster is provided which provides an overview of the project. On this poster all work packages are included as well.

Scientific Themes

The P2F project is composed of four scientific work streams (WSs) defined by key challenges in climate modelling. The fifth work stream covers the Outreach and Management of the project.

A short description of each scientific work streams can be found below. For an overview of the P2F project, please have a look at our [general poster](#).

WS1: Earth system model evaluation and improvement

Evaluate and improve Earth System Models through paleoclimate constraints. Our ambition is to radically advance Earth System models (ESMs) by integrating paleoclimate data into their development cycle, establishing a new paradigm for CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project). This involves improving models and tuning them using past conditions to produce more robust future climate projection.

WS2: Paleo data: observations, proxies, timeseries

We aim to compile, integrate and re-evaluate

Figure 10 Scientific Themes page

5.4 News

All P2F news items can be found on the *News page*. The news item posts on the website will link to the original article in case the news item was first published somewhere else. To enhance usability, different categories will be added once more content is created.

News

20/03/2025
An exciting launch for the P2F Team
 Last week in Utrecht, we kicked off our new P2F programme, bringing together researchers in mathematics, physics, geology, (palaeo-)biology, and...

03/03/2025
Project launched: improving climate models with historical data
 How can climate history help us create a more accurate picture of the future climate? A major European consortium, consisting...

Figure 11 News page

5.5 Events

An overview of upcoming P2F events is shown on the *Events page* with the events taking place in the nearest future listed on top. Events that are only for consortia members as well as events for a broader audience will be listed on this page. The possibility to integrate different filters will be explored. A template for Agenda Items is created to make sure that a clear and structured overview is provided, including the date and location of the event as well as information about registration will be provided.

Figure 12 Events page

5.6 Data Portal

On the *Data Portal page*, a link will be provided to the P2F data portal once available and an explanation is given on the purpose of the data portal, design ambitions and timeline of the implementation.

Data Portal

As part of the project we will create a data portal that will provide easy access to inter-operable paleo proxy data. The P2F data portal will be an enduring legacy for both data and modelling science communities.

Initially, the portal will be used internally within the project, with plans to release it to the wider scientific community at a later stage. Once the data portal is publicly available, we will share the link to it on this page.

Open access to curated paleoclimate data for research and collaboration

The P2F Data Portal is being developed as a central platform for accessing and sharing high-quality paleoclimate data within the P2F project. It will integrate newly generated datasets from across the project's work packages—covering proxies such as tree rings, marine sediments, and ice cores—as well as data from established repositories like PANGAEA and NOAA-NCEI. All data will follow FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), ensuring long-term usability by the wider scientific community.

The portal will feature an interactive map and advanced filtering tools, allowing users to search by region, time interval, proxy type, and more. It will also include metadata, highlight high-quality datasets, and support internal sharing of unpublished data.

Figure 13 Data Portal page

5.7 Publications

Once the first publications are out, they will be listed on the *Publications page*. At this point we will also decide on how to format the list.

Publications

All of P2F's scientific publications can be found on this page.

Figure 14 Publications page

5.8 P2F Internal

The *P2F Internal page* is accessible only via a password that will be shared with all consortia members. This page provides quick access to relevant links, documents, templates and project guidelines. The page will serve as an onboarding 'document' (page) on which new and current consortia members can find all information they need

to function within the project.

Figure 15 P2F Internal page

5.9 Contact

The *Contact* page includes the project’s email address p2f@uu.nl and an overview of the coordination team.

Figure 16 Contact page